

THE ROLE OF INTERACTIVE METHODS IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

Kenjebaeva Klara Berdimuratovna

Abdalieva Peruza Isaevna

Saparova Liza Xalmuratovna

Senior teachers of the Department of General Pedagogy and Psychology, Faculty of Primary Education. Nukus State Pedagogical Institute named after Ajiniyaz. The Republic of Uzbekistan. Nukus city.

Abstract: This article provides advice on how to use interactive methods in practical lessons and how to use the cluster method outside of class.

Keywords: interactive method, teacher, method, cluster, cluster approach, roadmap.

INTRODUCTION

Today's teacher is required to fulfill the responsible task entrusted to him seriously, to keep pace with the times in his professional activity. First of all, every teacher should approach his profession with love and responsibility, consider every hour of the lesson as sacred, consider every hour of the lesson as sacred, and feel that it is impossible to betray him in the slightest. For this, he should be able to thoroughly prepare for the daily lesson, use the most modern technologies in his work, and be able to ensure the quality and efficiency of the lesson.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

It was developed by the First President of our country, Islam Karimov, that it is natural to influence the development of society and the state at any level of education without identity. Life itself has shown the successful result of the National Personnel Training Program, which was implemented under his direct leadership and received the attention of world experts.

One of today's urgent tasks in general secondary education and higher educational institutions is the effective and appropriate use of advanced pedagogical technologies that serve to increase the effectiveness of education in classes.

Nowadays, one of the modern ways of organizing classes is the use of interactive methods. With the help of interactive methods, it is possible to encourage students in the process of making them active in each lesson, to create an opportunity to develop their mental activity independently.

In the lessons conducted on the basis of modern pedagogical interactive methods, the teacher and students deeply analyze the connection between disciplines and the essence of the topics. Critical situations are created in the lesson. Sometimes the teacher, and sometimes the students themselves, raise the problem and try to think and find a solution. A modern teacher needs to make every lesson interesting and meaningful. The teacher should use such a method that it does not take up too much time in the lesson, and neither the teacher nor the student face difficulties in using it. One such interactive method is the "Cluster" method.

The "Cluster" method is a specific form of pedagogical, didactic strategy, which helps students to create conditions for free, open thinking and free expression of ideas about optional problems.

RESEARCH RESULTS

This method requires the identification of a structure that allows thinking about the connections between different ideas. The "cluster" method is considered a form of thinking that is not directed to a specific object. Its use is based on the principle of human brain activity. This method serves to ensure that the activity of thinking is in harmony until a specific topic is mastered deeply and thoroughly by students. Clustering is a pedagogical strategy that helps students think freely and openly about a topic.

The word "cluster" means a group. It is advisable to use clustering on a topic before you have thoroughly studied the topic.

The sequence of creating a cluster method:

1. Write the key word and sentence in the center of a large piece of paper or on a classroom board or writing surface.
2. Write down the words and sentences that come to mind and are considered relevant to this topic.
3. Keep writing all the ideas that come to mind until you run out of ideas or time runs out.
4. The quoted words and thoughts are divided into categories depending on their content and proximity.

The "Cluster" method, developed in accordance with the idea of \u200b\u200bstyle and style, is a well-thought-out strategy that can be used with students individually or in groups.

The advantage of this interactive method is its results. Using a cluster has the following advantages:

- It involves the whole team in the learning process, it is interesting for them;

- Children speak actively and openly, they have no fear of making a mistake or expressing a wrong opinion.

In doing these things, the following knowledge skills will increase:

- skill of asking questions;
- to be able to distinguish the main one;
- establishing cause-and-effect relationships and building intelligent conclusions;
- transition from the personal to the general, understanding the problems as a whole;
- analysis and comparison;
- transfer of analogues.

DISCUSSION

What does the use of the cluster method give to children in lessons? Develops children's ability to think and express their thoughts. All this develops in the results of observation, in the experience of gaining new knowledge, in seeing several directions at the same time, in the creative analysis of information. The cluster method can be used in all types of lessons, on various topics. For example, we can also use this "Cluster" method effectively to check whether students are late to class or go home late after class. Can we say that this method is used in the course of the lesson? How can we check whether a student comes and goes to class, goes home late after class, using this method? A small question arises. We give our students a simple task to keep them interested. That is, in what directions do each of you travel from your homes to school? When you come to school, what do you see on your way (kindergarten, another school yard, swimming pool, sports ground, construction complexes, etc.), that is, we say draw a map of your movement.

CONCLUSION

From the maps drawn by our students, we will be able to find out what roads they take and where they stop. Based on this map drawn by them, we can find out the safety of their roads, where they stay, in which vehicles and in which directions they arrive.

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